

COMPOUND AND COMPLEX (DAS SATZGEFÜGE) SENTENCES IN GERMAN

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Abstract: This article examines how compound sentences and complex sentences are made in German, and their structural types. At the same time, it has been shown that conjunctions play an important role in connecting parts of lexical elements that are often not combined.

Key words: simple conjunction, complex conjunction, conjunction, definite article, additional article, sentences, verbs.

Sentences are simple and complex, and complex, in turn, are divided into compound and complex.

Compound sentences consist of equal parts, which are connected by coordinating conjunctions, which we talked about in previous lessons. These unions can change the order of words or leave everything as it is. In this lesson, we will talk about the second type of complex sentences - complex sentences. Features of the structure of complex sentences. Thus, complex sentences are made up of a main clause and a subordinate clause. The subordinate clause is connected to the main clause and is connected to it with the help of subordinate clauses. In addition to subordinating conjunctions, relative pronouns (with or without a conjunction) and adverbial clauses can also be used to link. Some complex sentences may not be joined.

There are several types of supplements. They give different meanings to the sentence. The main types of adjectives:

- adverbial clauses with conjunction dass (what), ob (or);
- attributive sentences with relative pronouns say (which),
Die, das, die -(which);
- adverbs weil (because), da (because);
- tense adjectives als (when) während (now) and others;
- conjunctive clauses wenn (if), falls (if in case);
- concessions subject to trade unions obwohl (although) etc.;
- goals subject to the alliance curse(to) and others.

It is very important to remember that the predicate is at the end of the main clause. The predicate is often a verb. Intransitive and compound parts appear when we have a modal verb, for example. **Ich kann kommen.** kann is the conjugated part, kommen is the invariant part. There are several types of adverbial clauses. Below we present a table of types of subordinate clauses, including introductory words (conjunctions, pronouns), followed by the above word order in the subordinate clause.

The main types of subordinate clauses:

1) Reasons:

Ich mache das Fenster auf, da es mir zu heiss ist. I open the window because it's too hot for me.

2) Objectives:

Ich lerne Deutsch, dann ich eine gute Arbeit finden kann. I am learning German so I can get a good job.

I came to Deutschland to learn German. I came to Germany to learn German.

3) Conditions:

Wenn es morgen nicht regnet, gehen wir in die Berge. If it doesn't rain tomorrow, we will climb the mountain.

4) Time:

Wenn du nach Hause kommst, ruf mich bitte an. Call me when you get home.

Während ich arbeite, sind meine Kinder im Kindergarten. My children are in kindergarten while I work.

5) Places and directions:

Ich möchte wissen, wo wir sind. I want to know where we are.

6) Benefits:

Although it is raining, gehe ich spazieren. Even if it's raining, I go for a walk.

7) Comparison:

Je mehr Geld ich verdiene, desto mehr Steuern muss ich bezahlen. The more money I earn, the more taxes I have to pay.

Additional adverb

Können Sie mir bitte sagen, wie dieses Gerät funktioniert? Can you tell me how this device works?

Ich weiss noch nothing, ob ich morgen ins Schwimmbad gehe. I don't know yet if I will go to the pool tomorrow.

Definite article

I would like to marry a man who will always understand me. I want to marry someone who will always understand me.

Grammatically simple sentences (SPs) consisting of the equivalent of German SSPs, which can be two or more sentences in number. The communication of proposals in SSP can be allied and non-alliance. Trade unions participating in the construction of BSC are called coordinators. In the absence of conjunctions or compound words that replace them, adverbs and allied words with adverbs, individual sentences are combined into complex sentences using only intonation.

Speaking of coordinating conjunctions, it should be noted that they do not combine simple sentences (PP) into a whole. They can also connect homogeneous members, for example:

• *Willst du ein Gedicht oder ein Lied vortragen?* - *Do you want to read a poem or sing a song (homogeneous adverbs in German)?*

German unions can be of two pairs. Such associations can connect both homogeneous members and separate PPs, for example:

• *Zu Hause hat er neither Fleisch nor Gemüse.* - *At home, he has neither meat nor vegetables (homogeneous additions within PP).*

• *Dort wird sie nicht nur lernen, sondern auch sich erholen.* - *There he not only studies, but also rests (homogeneous predicates in the scope of PP).*

Conjunctions are connectives without clauses. This is their main difference from allied words. Compound words are suitable parts of sentences and affect word order. Consider examples of BSC with compound words:

- *Klaus macht immer alle Hausaufgaben, darum lernt er gut. Klaus always does all his homework, so he studies well.*
- *Das Wetter ist regnerisch, trotzdem spielen die Kinder gern im Hof. It's rainy, but despite this, the children willingly play in the yard.*

If there are 2 (or more) predicates in a sentence, this scheme is called a compound sentence. These prepositions can be separated by commas or conjunctions. Example with conjunction: "Das Auto faehrt und das Flugzeug fliegt" - The car is driving and the plane is flying. Example with a comma: "Mein Bruder geht heute arbeiten, ich gehe derzeit zum Deutschkurs" - My brother is going to work today, meanwhile I am going to German courses. Sentences are constructed without any deviations from the usual scheme of sentence construction. In fact, we have two main offers rolled into one.

Coordinating compounds:

Complex sentences:

When there is a subordinate clause in a sentence, the scheme is called a complex sentence. The main question that interests us in this topic is how the subordinate clause is structured. To begin with, let's define what is a subordinate clause and what is the main one. Very simply, the subordinate clause expresses the main clause, and the main clause expresses the main idea. Example: I am going by car because the weather is bad outside. "I go by car" preposition; "because the weather is bad" is an adjective.

Another subordinate clause is easy to identify by union. All prepositional phrases begin with a preposition. In the example above, the conjunction was the phrase "because".

What subordinating conjunctions do we have?

Basic connectives (dass - what (affirmation), weil - because, da - since, wenn - when (affirmation, present or future tense) / if, als - when (affirmation, past tense), obwohl - although)

References:

1. Devkin V.D. Entertaining lexicology. - M.: Humanitarian publishing center VLADOS, 1998. - 312 p.
2. Devkin V.D. Features of German colloquial speech. - Moscow: International relations. - 1965. - 308 p.
3. Mikhailov L.M. Grammar of German Dialogic Speech: Textbook for Foreign Faculties and Institutes of Foreign Languages. - M.: Higher School, 1986. - 110 p.
4. German colloquial speech. Morphological, phonetic and syntactic features. Online-Teacher.ru.6. Salomov RS., Sharipov A.K. Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va uslubiyati. Darslik. T.: «ITA-PRESS», 2015.182 bet.
7. Goncharova O.V. "Yosh sportchilarning jismoniy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish" o'quv qo'llanma T.: O'zDJTI nashriyoti 2005 y.

